

ICLC 2024 - Proposal for Open Submissions: Video

1. General Information

- **Video Title:** Way of Schesa
- **Affiliation (institution, community, etc.):** Arizona State University & State University of New York
- **Main Contact:** Shawn Lawson
- **Key Contributors:** Ryan Ross Smith
- **Duration:** 15 minutes

2. Video Description

Lawson and Smith (aka Obi Wan Codenobi and The Wookie), set out on a new adventure across the galaxy. They settle into an interstitial span of hyperspace travel while cruising the uncharted territories near the Chiss Ascendancy. Tsiraki is poured and AlgoChill is starting to come over the speakers. Codenobi and Wookie unwind into these fleeting moments between endless battles and negotiations.

This new AlgoChill is reminiscent of traveling among millions stars and yet, using the force to bend and shape them. Sonically bringing their formations and constellations to life into patterns and wisps of smoke, coxing signal from noise. Could this be how the ozyly-esehembo (sky-walkers) envision hyperspace routes without navigation computers?

Wookie performs tidal cycles with custom made samples. Codenobi performs python and the opengl fragment shader on more than 4 million particles. The visual output is rendered at 30 fps in 4k UHD TV (3840 x 2160) resolution.

3. Video Link

<https://vimeo.com/912066403/a73d08f7c5>

4. Biography

Shawn Lawson is a computational artist and researcher creating the computational sublime. He performs under the pseudonym Obi-Wan Codenobi where he live-codes real-time computer graphics and neural nets with his open source software. Lawson has performed, exhibited, or screened in museums, galleries, festivals, and public space across five continents. Lawson has published in a wide range of international technical and arts conferences and journals. His work has been funded by national and international agencies. Lawson studied fine arts at Carnegie Mellon University and École Nationale Supérieure des Beaux-Arts

and received his MFA from the School of the Art Institute of Chicago. He is an Professor and Animation Program Director at Arizona State University.

Ryan Ross Smith is a composer, performer, sound designer, engineer and educator currently based in New York. Smith has performed throughout the US, Europe and UK, including performances at MoMA and PS1 and Le Centre Pompidou, has had his music performed throughout North America, Iceland, Denmark, Australia and the UK, has presented his work and research at conferences including NIME, ISEA, ICLI, ICLC, SMF, ACMC and TENOR, and has lectured at various colleges and universities. Smith is known for his work with Animated Notation, and his Ph.D. research website is archived at animatednotation.com. Current & recent projects include Duets [remotely-produced duets with musical friends from around the globe], Lines and Patterns [musique concrete disguised as ambient music], Green Dome [with Zeena Parkins and Ryan Sawyer], Ross Farwell [IDM/Breakbeat] and Sequential Switch [daily modular synthesizer project]. Smith is currently an Assistant Professor of Music at the State University of New York.